

The background of the cover features a network diagram with various colored nodes (blue, red, black, green) connected by thin white lines. The background color transitions from light green at the top to a darker teal at the bottom.

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Job Satisfaction as Correlates of Librarians' Job Performance in Selected University Libraries in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated job satisfaction as it correlates with librarians' job performance in university libraries in Delta and Edo States. Three research questions and one hypothesis were tested. The research used descriptive and correlational survey design and involved 133 librarians as the population drawn from federal, state, and private universities across two South- South States. The total enumerative sampling technique was adopted due to small size of the population. Data were collected using a questionnaire titled "job satisfaction, as correlates of librarians' job performance in university libraries in Delta and Edo States Questionnaire," which underwent face and content validation. Reliability was established with a 0.85 coefficient using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Data analysis was conducted according to the study objectives. ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis. The criterion mean that was used for this study was 3.00. The study revealed that librarians in University libraries carry out various responsibilities to support users' academic and research needs. Librarians in University libraries frequently performed user education, reference services, cataloguing and classification, orientation services, lending services, acquisition, and referral services. Librarians in university libraries in Delta and Edo States experienced a high extent of job satisfaction. Proper library's physical environment, supporting productivity, clear promotion criteria, regular salary review, continuous professional development, and completing assigned tasks are the indicators of job satisfaction among librarians in University libraries in Delta and Edo States. There is a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among librarians in university libraries in Delta and Edo States as higher job satisfaction positively influences job performance among librarians in University libraries in Delta and Edo States. The study recommends that Library managers should remain focused on activities that increase job satisfaction and increasing commitment of the librarians. Also, the library management should sustain the job satisfaction levels of librarians by providing innovative ways of making library tasks interesting and challenging. The university management should motivate the librarians, because when librarians are motivated, it makes them to be satisfied with their jobs, hence improve the service quality they render to users.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Correlates, Librarians, Job Performance, University Libraries, South-South, Nigeria

Introduction

Librarians play pivotal roles in the delivery of services in any form of library where they work which the university library is not exempted from. University libraries are set up to meet the needs of the university community. The needs of users fall under diverse categories of library functions like provision of informational, educational, research, aesthetic fulfillment, cultural and recreational resources including the provision of different library services, etc. The resources and services they provide create opportunities for learning, support literacy and education, and help shape the new ideas and perspectives that are central to an ingenious and innovative society. For these reasons, librarians are expected to perform optimally at their jobs.

Job performance of librarians promotes and supports the social environment for the improvement of in-role which engenders effective and high productivity. It is the discharge of statutory duties based on the field of specialization of library personnel which is centered on the attainment of the library objectives. It should be noted that job performance has become a significant indicator in determining organizational performance. Based on this, it can be said that the generality of library performance is based on the job performance of the librarians in the organization. Oluloye (2020) asserted that librarians perform their statutory roles in order to accomplish the set goals of their libraries. Therefore, librarians are the most important in resource management in each library. The attitude of the librarians towards their duties is very important in the achievement of high level of performance in assigned tasks. It is the duty of the librarian to offer better services to users and to make sure that information sources and services are well employed for users' information needs.

Personal observation by the researcher, from visits to other libraries and discussions with colleagues, indicate that librarians have not been meeting the expected level of job performance in their libraries, especially in this present study locale. Scholars have pointed to the fact that the job performances of librarians in Nigerian

universities have not been meeting the set levels of expectation in certain tasks. Consequently, Akor (2009) found out that the job performance of librarians in the North Central zone of Nigeria is on a very low level. In terms of publications output, Amusa *et al.* (2013), as well as Babalola and Nwalo (2013) also reported a low job performance of librarians. In the same light, Mohammad (2015) asserted that there is no designated directory based on services delivery available in libraries to locate library websites and no scholarly literature has been written on the topic on behalf of the institute of users' education programme services and photocopies are also inadequate.

Job satisfaction, on the other hand, has been identified as an important element in determining the job performance of employees in any given organization set out to make an impact in its area of specialty. The concept of job satisfaction as identified by Hussain and Soroya (2017), are a set of psychological, physiological and environmental factors that leads to a person's feeling of contentment with their job. This, therefore, means that job satisfaction entails how happy library employees are with their work as well as the emotional mindset that allows them to do their duty with zeal, energy and without complaints. Job satisfaction of employees plays a crucial role in determining the general productivity of workers in any organization. It can be defined as an emotional response to a job situation which cannot be seen, but only be inferred. It is simply regarded as how people feel about their job and different aspects of it. Job satisfaction means a positive attitude that an individual has from what he does to earn a living. Hence, Gamlath and Kaluarachchi (2024) viewed job satisfaction as the rate at which employees like or dislike their work and the extent to which their expectations concerning work have been fulfilled. Job satisfaction is generally acknowledged as a necessary ingredient for personal fulfillment in carrying out one's duties.

Kaur (2022) pointed out the need for job satisfaction stating that satisfied librarians are more likely to put in more effort on their jobs than their less satisfied colleagues. Anyaoku *et al.* (2018) affirmed that where a librarian is dissatisfied with his or her job, there is a tendency

for the display of negative attitude towards users. In Pakistan, Khan and Ahmed (2019), carried out a study on the job satisfaction of library professionals in public universities and arrived at the conclusion that they were slightly satisfied. In a similar manner, in Nigeria, Onuoha *et al.* (2024), examined the job satisfaction of library personnel in private universities in Ogun State and affirmed moderate positive level of job satisfaction among library employees while reporting stringent conditions for promotion, denied access to benefits and lack of job security as major constraints to job satisfaction.

According to Lim (2018), studies have shown diverse results when it comes to the job satisfaction of librarians. With respect to age, Kuo and Chen (2024) found that the older employees were more satisfied with their jobs than the younger ones. On the other hand, other researchers have found that environment is not a major factor correlating with an employee's job satisfaction (Chwe, 2019; Lynch & Verdin, 2019; Hovekamp, 2019). But Tella *et al.* (2017) demonstrated that there is a correlation between work environment and experience and the job satisfaction of librarians in Nigeria. Some earlier studies also showed that job satisfaction correlates with organizational commitment. This study, therefore, aims to explore the relationship that exists among work environment, job satisfaction and librarians' job performance in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Librarians' job performance is central to the success of university libraries, which play a vital role in supporting teaching, research, and academic development. University libraries are also crucial to the accreditation of academic programmes, and their effectiveness relies heavily on the productivity and commitment of librarians. These professionals are responsible for a wide range of tasks, including acquisition, cataloguing, classification, shelving, weeding, evaluation of resources, and delivering specialized services to meet institutional goals. Effective performance in these roles depends largely on job satisfaction. A well-structured, adequately resourced, and supportive work setting enhances staff morale and performance, while poor working conditions can lead to

dissatisfaction and reduced productivity. In university libraries across south- south, Nigeria, librarians often face unfavourable work environments characterized by poor lighting, inadequate furniture, insufficient ICT infrastructure, irregular salary payments, excessive workload, limited promotion opportunities, poor supervision, and weak interpersonal relationships.

These challenges have been shown to negatively impact job satisfaction and performance. If left unaddressed, these issues may continue to hinder the performance of librarians, leading to poor library service delivery, reduced patronage, and diminished academic outcomes. This study therefore, investigates the extent to which job satisfaction correlate with librarians' job performance in selected university libraries in south-south, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine library work environment, job satisfaction as it correlates with librarians' job performance in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. examine the types of job performed by librarians in selected university libraries in South- South, Nigeria.
2. investigate the extent to which librarians are satisfied with their job in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria; and,
3. determine the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the types of jobs performed by librarians in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are librarians satisfied with their jobs in university libraries in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

A single null hypothesis was formulated and tested in this study at a 0.05 level of significance:

HO1: There is no significant relationship between satisfaction and librarians' job performance in selected university libraries in South-South, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Jobs performed by librarians are frameworks of activities or operations put in place by the library to ensure that users or patrons utilize information materials made available in the library. Imeremba (2011) saw jobs of librarians as various library activities or operations carried out to satisfy user's information needs. The study of Aina (2014) pointed out that librarians perform different types of jobs like; current awareness services, reference services, display, accession lists, library publications, literacy programmes, extension services, on-line services exhibition, user education, literature search, selective dissemination of information, referral services and outreach services. Consequently, Iwuagwu and Uko (2012) emphasized that the roles of librarians in university libraries were to provide information services to users on request and maximization of resources as one of the principles underlying the concept of library services.

The study of Ogbomo (2015) asserted that librarians perform bibliographic verification services to users and orientation activities, reprographic services (Okolo, 2023). The study of Onadokun (2019) expressed that extension/community services are also services performed by librarians in university libraries, while Omorodion (2023) stated that librarians carried out user education services, Gbaji (2017) stated some services performed by librarians includes collection management, systems department so that users can gain free access into the systems department of the library such as computers or automation department so as to be able to search their information needs online, cataloguing and classification to facilitate easy access to the information resources. Digital initiatives programme to oversees the selective digitization of the university's manuscript

collection and other records, and indexing and abstracting services (Gbaji, 2017).

On the extent of job satisfaction by librarians, a study was carried out by Kashin (2021) noted a low extent of job satisfaction among the librarians and this make then to demonstrate high level of lateness to work abandoning of duties. For Kaba (2017), the extent of satisfaction for library professionals working in these institutions is moderate. Kaba (20217) spotted revision of service structure, promotion policies, and improvement in academic qualifications and advance training were measures to improve the services of the library professionals in theses public institutions. Correspondingly, Memon and Jena (2017) expressed that library professionals from private engineering and management college job satisfaction is high. In the same light, Hart (2011) noted the extent of job satisfaction among library heads was high.

Consequently, Ekere and Ugwu (2011) hold that job satisfaction among older librarians is higher compared to the younger ones. In the same manner, the authors expressed that gender and work experience are not significant factor that influences job satisfaction of librarians. Still, Horestein (2023) noted a high extent of job satisfaction by librarians with academic rank than non-faculty groups. Subsequently, Ayele (2022) noted that an extent of satisfaction for lower cadre of library staff was low while the extent of job satisfaction for higher cadre of staff were higher. Also, Fyneman and Zoukemefa (2023) saw an extent of job satisfaction among librarians was high. Ola and Adeyemi (2022) while investigating motivation and job satisfaction of library personnel in colleges of education libraries expressed the extent to which librarians are satisfied with their job was low. However, the researcher identified that the morale of staff in the target group was doused due to frustration resulting from lack of involvement in decision making and inadequate recognition among others are research why the job satisfaction of librarians is low.

Correspondingly, job satisfaction of employees plays a very vital role on their performance in any organization (Latif *et al.*, 2014; Perera *et al.*, 2014). Bockerman and Ilmakunnas (2020) noted

that sickness, absences, accidents, job quits, self-reported performance measures, and supervisors' evaluations of their employees' performance. For Dhanapal *et al.* (2013); Hossain (2014); Khan and Parveen (2014), job satisfaction has relative effect on the overall job performance of employees in the light of organizational current realities. Hence, both motivational and job satisfaction factors are inter-related; both factors enhance the productivity of librarians in the university community.

Pushpakumari (2018) noted that positive attitude of librarians has a direct relationship with the level of their productivity; it affects the rate at which information can be processed and effectively disseminated to the information seeker. The author stressed that a satisfied work force will create a pleasant atmosphere within the organization to perform well. The result of the author's study showed that there exists positive correlation between job satisfaction and performance of employees. According to Salami (2018), librarians who are more satisfied with their jobs are more committed and perform better. In a study of private sector employees, Warsi *et al.* (2019) showed that overall job satisfaction predicted organizational commitment. They found out that organizations would only need to increase and maintain two variables (work motivation and job satisfaction) to achieve the positive effect on the services performed. Niehoff (2017) found that a significant but small correlation exists between job satisfaction and job performance. There were also the results from authors who had shown that

the relationship between job satisfaction and librarians' job performance was reciprocal. That is, librarians' commitment in meeting the needs of users was from job satisfaction and in turn influenced an employee's decision to remain or leave the organization. The implication of this result is that job satisfaction and job performance can influence each other.

Methodology

In this study, a correlational descriptive survey approach was employed. 133 librarians working in government owned and private owned university libraries in selected university libraries in south-south, Nigeria. However, the concentration of this study shall center on university libraries in Delta and Edo States. Total enumeration sampling method was adopted due to the small size of the study. Osuala (2021) noted that the entire population can be included in the study when there is a sizable enough population. The instruments for data collection was questionnaire and a 133 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 97(73%) were returned. The response rate of 60% is considered adequate for the study because the standard and acceptable response rate for most studies is 60%. In the opinion of Baxter and Babbie (2004), a response rate of 60% and above is considered adequate for analysis and reporting. Similarly, Fincham (2008) noted that researchers should aim for a response rate of about 60% in most studies.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the types of jobs performed by you in your library?

Table 1: Types of Jobs Performed by Librarians

S/N	Types of jobs performed by librarians	A		D	
		No.	%	No.	%
1.	Audio/visual service	44	45.4	53	54.6
2.	Online book reservation	42	43.3	55	56.7
3.	Announcement	53	54.6	44	45.4
4.	Current awareness services for library resources	64	66.0	33	34.0
5.	Telephone services	37	38.1	60	61.9
6.	Research help service	73	75.3	24	24.7
7.	Selective dissemination of information	74	76.3	23	23.7
8.	Inter-library loan services	64	66.0	33	34.0
9.	Indexing and abstracting services	72	74.2	25	25.8

10.	Extension and outreach services	41	42.3	56	57.7
11.	Reprographic services	63	64.9	34	35.1
12.	Lending services	80	82.5	17	17.5
13.	Internet browsing	71	73.2	26	26.8
14.	Online public access card services (OPAC)	60	61.9	37	38.1
15.	User education	86	88.7	11	11.3
16.	Reference services	83	85.6	14	14.4
17.	Referral services	77	79.4	20	20.6
18.	Orientation services	81	83.5	16	16.5
19.	Acquisition	84	86.6	13	13.4
20.	Cataloguing and classification	82	84.5	15	15.5

Table 1 reveals a broad range of professional responsibilities the librarians carry out. The data shows that librarians predominantly engage in core library functions that support users' academic and research needs. Notably, the most commonly performed jobs include user education (88.7%), reference services (85.6%), cataloguing and classification (84.5%), orientation services (83.5%), lending services (82.5%), acquisition (86.6%), and referral services (79.4%). These figures indicate a strong emphasis on traditional library roles that facilitate information access, resource organisation, and user guidance.

In addition to these, a significant number of librarians are also involved in services that support research and digital literacy. These include- selective dissemination of information (76.3%), research help services (75.3%), indexing and abstracting services (74.2%), and internet browsing (73.2%). Engagement in online public access catalogue (OPAC) services (61.9%) and current awareness services (66.0%) also

reflects the librarians' involvement in promoting resource visibility and accessibility. However, certain services recorded lower levels of librarian participation. These include telephone services (38.1%), audio/visual services (45.4%), online book reservations (43.3%), and extension and outreach services (42.3%). The relatively low engagement in these areas may be attributed to infrastructural limitations, low user demand, or lack of specialized training or support systems. Overall, the findings demonstrate that librarians in selected university libraries in south-south, Nigeria are actively performing a wide range of job functions, with a stronger presence in academic-centered and user-support services, while modern technological services and outreach activities are less frequently undertaken. This highlights the need for continuous professional development and infrastructure enhancement to enable librarians to diversify and expand their service delivery.

Research Question 2: To what extent are you satisfied with your job in your library?

Table 2: Extent of Librarians Job Satisfaction

S/N	Extent of job satisfaction	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	Std.
1.	I feel valued as a staff of my library team	43	33	10	6	5	4.06	1.13
2.	Clear promotion criteria would enhance job satisfaction	52	34	6	3	2	4.35	0.89
3.	I feel higher education would enhance job prospects	47	37	8	2	3	4.27	0.93
4.	I feel confident in my ability to adapt to changing library trends	33	45	10	5	4	4.01	1.02
5.	I am satisfied with the training and development programs put in place by my library management	24	31	10	19	13	3.35	1.39
6.	I am satisfied with management policies in my library	21	26	20	19	11	3.28	1.31

7.	In my library, worker's sense of achievement boosts job satisfaction	30	45	14	3	5	3.95	1.02
8.	I am satisfied with my library conducive work environment	22	37	26	2	10	3.61	1.17
9.	Library work requires continuous professional development	54	27	9	3	4	4.28	1.04
10.	Completing assigned tasks enhances my level of job satisfaction	48	37	4	3	5	4.24	1.04
11.	Library policies accommodate family needs	22	37	19	11	8	3.56	1.20
12.	My supervisor is approachable and open to feedback	38	33	11	8	7	3.90	1.22
13.	My age helps me connect better with library patrons	33	35	23	2	4	3.94	1.02
14.	I am satisfied with the healthy, clean, and conducive work environment	29	29	27	7	5	3.72	1.13
15.	I am satisfied when the library parent institution permits and highly values the research of academic librarians.	45	29	12	5	6	4.05	1.17
16.	I feel satisfied with the way tasks are evenly distributed among library staff	29	26	24	11	7	3.61	1.23
17.	The policies in my library align with organizational goals	35	36	17	5	4	3.96	1.06
18.	My religious beliefs are respected in my place of work	40	34	18	2	3	4.09	0.98
19.	Regular salary review would improve workers' morale	55	26	9	3	4	4.29	1.04
20.	The library's physical environment could support productivity	55	31	7	0	4	4.37	0.94
21.	I feel satisfied with training on automated systems	26	22	16	23	10	3.32	1.37
22.	Effective management policies would lead to a positive working environment	54	27	8	2	6	4.25	1.11
Aggregate Mean/Std.							3.93	1.11
Criterion Mean							3.00	

The aggregate mean score of 3.93 with a standard deviation of 1.11 is significantly higher than the criterion mean of 3.00, suggesting that respondents perceived themselves as being highly satisfied with their jobs. Notably, items such as the library's physical environment supporting productivity ($\bar{x} = 4.37$), clear promotion criteria enhancing job satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 4.35$), regular salary review improving workers' morale ($\bar{x} = 4.29$), the need for continuous professional

development ($\bar{x} = 4.28$), and completing assigned tasks ($\bar{x} = 4.24$) received the highest mean scores, indicating key drivers of satisfaction among librarians. Therefore, it can be concluded that librarians in selected university libraries in south-south, Nigeria experience a high extent of job satisfaction.

Table 3: Relationship between Satisfaction and Job Performance of Librarians

		The extent of job satisfaction	The extent of job performance
The extent of job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.624**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	97	97
The extent of job performance	Pearson Correlation	.624**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	97	97

The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.624$) indicates a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among librarians in university libraries in Delta and Edo States. The p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) is 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, suggesting that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a strong, positive, and significant relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among librarians in university

libraries in selected university libraries in south-south, Nigeria.

Testing of the Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between satisfaction and librarians' job performance in university libraries in selected university libraries in south- south, Nigeria.

Table 4.12: Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Librarians' Job Performance

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.491 ^a	.241	.233		.62446
ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11.767	1	11.767	30.175	.000 ^b
Residual	37.046	95	.390		
Total	48.813	96			
Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.440	.278		8.766	.000
Job Satisfaction	.390	.071	.491	5.493	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Librarians' Job Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction

The relationship between job satisfaction and librarians' job performance in university libraries in Delta and Edo States was analysed using linear regression. The model summary revealed that the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.241, indicating that 24.1% of the variance in librarians' job performance can be explained by job satisfaction. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.233 suggests that the model provides a moderate

explanation of the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance.

The ANOVA results show that the F-value is 30.175, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that the overall model is statistically significant. This suggests that job satisfaction has a significant effect on librarians' job performance. Looking at the individual coefficients, job satisfaction ($B =$

0.390, $p = 0.000$) shows a positive and statistically significant relationship with job performance. The beta value of 0.491 indicates that higher job satisfaction positively influences job performance among librarians. Since the p -value is less than 0.05, one can reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among librarians in university libraries in selected university libraries in south- south, Nigeria.

Discussions

Librarians in university libraries carry out various responsibilities to support users' academic and research needs. They frequently performed in the university libraries to include user education, reference services, cataloguing and classification, orientation services, lending services, acquisition, and referral services. However, librarians do not frequently perform services like telephone services, audio/visual services, online book reservations, extension and outreach service. Findings in this study align with Aina (2014) who opined that librarians in university libraries perform different types of jobs like; current awareness services, reference services, display, accession lists, library publications, literacy programmes, extension services, on-line services exhibition, user education, literature search, selective dissemination of information, referral services and outreach services. In the same vein, the findings of this study corresponds with that of Ahiauzu (2019) who opined that librarians in university libraries perform jobs such as inter-library relations, lending services, inter-library loan services, reprographic services, selective dissemination of information (SDI), abstracting and indexing services as well as translation services to members of the university communities.

The extents to which librarians are satisfied with their job in university libraries in research question four reveal that librarians in university libraries are highly satisfied with their jobs. Again, the findings in the study also prove that library's physical environment, supporting productivity, clear promotion criteria, regular

salary review which improve workers' morale, continuous professional development, and completing assigned tasks are the indicators of satisfaction among librarians in university libraries. More so, findings in this study correspond with that of Fyneman and Zoukemefa (2023) who stated that the extent of job satisfaction among librarians was high. Again, the finding in this study is in line with Nwankwere and Magaji (2016) who noted a high extent of job satisfaction among librarians in university libraries. Furthermore, the findings in this study agreed with that of Natter (2020) who stated that the extent of job satisfaction among librarians was high.

There is a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among librarians in university libraries in Delta and Edo States. Findings in this study is in line with Oswald *et al.* (2024) who stated that a relationship between job satisfaction and librarians' job performance in the organization had beneficial effects which also include increased work performance. Similarly, the findings in this study collaborate with Dhanapal *et al.* (2013); Hossain (2014); Khan and Parveen (2014) who noted that job satisfaction had relative effect on the overall job performance of employees in the light of organizational current realities. Hence, both motivational and job satisfaction factors are inter-related and enhance the productivity of librarians in the university community. Furthermore, the findings in this study concur with Salami (2018) who asserted that librarians who are more satisfied with their jobs are more committed and perform better.

Implications

Librarians in university libraries need to regularly up-skills their capacities on a regular basis. In this regard, there is need for librarians to constantly involve in trainings and re-training for them to continuously render/ deliver quality library services to the university Community. Librarians need to continuously perform their jobs for them to meet the information needs of users. More so, there is need for librarians to undergo training so that those jobs or services they don't

render/perform frequently can be carried out effectively and efficiently. Also, the university management needs to ensure that all indicating factors that make librarians to be satisfied with their job are put in place so that they can perform their work better. Good office equipment, good remunerations and harmonious working environment need to be made available to ensure that librarians in the university libraries performed their jobs to the best of their abilities.

Conclusion

Conclusively, while university libraries are depending on librarians to achieve their visions and missions, it is necessary that they (libraries) provide measure to make librarians to find satisfaction with their jobs. Based on the research findings, it is concluded that librarians in university libraries in Delta and Edo States engage in a broad range of professional responsibilities and core library functions like reference services, cataloguing and classification, orientation services, lending services, acquisition, referral services, resource organization, and user guidance to support users' academic and research needs. Librarians in university libraries experience a high extent of job satisfaction. There is a strong relationship between job satisfaction and job performance of librarians in selected university libraries in south-south, Nigeria. More so, the following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study:

1. University libraries should ensure that they render severity of services to users. This is important in the sense that when the services are limited, few people will patronize the library, but when the service is more, the libraries will have more people visiting.
2. Library managers should remain focused on activities that increase job satisfaction and increasing commitment of the librarians. Also, the library management should sustain the job satisfaction levels of librarians by providing innovative ways of making library tasks interesting and challenging. The university management should motivate the librarians, because when librarians are

motivated, it make them to be satisfied with their jobs, hence improve the service quality they render to users.

3. Financial and non-financial rewards are necessary for job satisfaction; hence, library management should look into ways of investing in staff welfare while also ensuring prompt payment of salaries.

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